

Energy Efficiency of Android Architectural Patterns: A Scenario-Based Study

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Abstract – Battery capacity remains a critical constraint for mobile applications, yet the energy impact of architectural design decisions remains largely unexplored. While previous studies have compared Android architectural patterns in terms of testability and performance, comprehensive evaluations of energy consumption across different usage scenarios are still lacking. Therefore, we systematically compare the energy efficiency of five Android architectures: MVC, MVP, Classic MVVM, Single-State MVVM, and MVI. By applying Clean Architecture principles and using identical Jetpack Compose UI components, we implemented normalized versions of each pattern and measured energy consumption with Android's BatteryManager API. We evaluated three realistic scenarios: chat streaming, shopping cart management, and product browsing. Our findings indicate that no single architecture is universally optimal, as scenario-specific workload characteristics determine energy efficiency. While MVC demonstrates better overall efficiency and performs better in chat streaming and shopping scenarios, MVI provides the best performance in UI-intensive product browsing. With Android's ecosystem of over 3 billion devices, this underscores the substantial sustainability implications of informed architectural decisions.

Keywords – Android, Architectural Patterns, Energy Consumption, Mobile Applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile applications have become ubiquitous in daily life, with battery capacity remaining a critical constraint that significantly limits user experience. Studies demonstrate that energy-inefficient applications are quickly uninstalled by users, with battery consumption consistently ranked as a primary concern for both developers and end-users [1]. While significant research has focused on hardware-level optimizations and operating system power management, the impact of architectural decisions on energy consumption remains underexplored [2], [3]. Understanding how architectural patterns influence energy efficiency is important, as early design decisions are costly to change.

This research gap is particularly significant given the scale of Android's deployment, with more than 3 billion active Android devices worldwide [4]. Even modest improvements in efficiency can lead to substantial aggregate energy savings and sustainability benefits. Understanding how architectural decisions impact energy consumption is critical, as mobile applications perform increasingly complex operations—from real-time communication to UI-intensive rendering-making foundational architectural choices essential for sustainable software engineering practices.

To address this gap, we present a study that systematically evaluates the energy efficiency of five Android architecture patterns: MVC, MVP, Classic MVVM, Single-State MVVM, and MVI. We have explored how the choice of architectural pattern influences energy consumption in Android applications across different usage scenarios, considering the specific characteristics of each workload to inform architectural decision-making. To do that, we implemented each of the five architectures (MVC, MVP, Classic MVVM,

Single-State MVVM, MVI) with identical functionality and measured their energy consumption across three realistic usage scenarios (chat streaming, shopping cart, and product browsing). The experiments were conducted with thermal conditions carefully controlled to prevent temperature fluctuations from influencing the energy measurements, using five iterations per scenario and a total of 75 measurements.

Our findings demonstrate that no single architectural pattern is universally optimal; instead, energy efficiency varies depending on the specific workload. For example, MVC outperforms other patterns in real-time and transactional scenarios, whereas MVI is more efficient in UI-intensive tasks. The study also identifies two consistent architecture-scenario vulnerabilities: MVI exhibits a 60% energy spike in chat streaming, while MVC shows a similar spike in product browsing. Furthermore, although individual device differences may appear small, the global scale of Android's deployment underscores the importance of making informed architectural decisions for sustainable development. These results challenge the assumption that architectural patterns have comparable energy consumption and offer valuable insights for optimizing energy efficiency based on application-specific needs.

II. RELATED WORK

Research on Android architectural patterns has primarily focused on code quality metrics and development productivity. For example, Tian conducted a comparative analysis of MVC, MVP, and MVVM, concluding that MVP and MVVM provide superior testability and maintainability compared to MVC [5]. Wisnuadhi et al. expanded this work by evaluating performance characteristics of MVP and MVVM, and MVVM demonstrates slight better CPU efficiency (0.55% improvement) while MVP exhibits lower memory consumption [6]. However, these studies have not addressed energy consumption, which is a critical non-functional requirement for mobile applications.

Energy profiling of mobile applications has progressed through both hardware-based and software-based methodologies. Hardware approaches, which use external power monitors, provide high accuracy, but require specialized equipment, limiting their accessibility [3], [7]. Software-based alternatives, such as Android's BatteryManager API, offer practical and accessible measurement capabilities. Groza et al. validated the Charge \times Voltage methodology for energy profiling, demonstrating reliable measurements for code smell analysis [8]. PowDroid showed that software-based energy profiling on individual devices provides sufficient accuracy for relative comparisons, reporting energy differences of 33–86% between Android applications [9]. Android's official documentation confirms that, while absolute accuracy may vary, consistent relative comparisons are still valuable for architectural evaluation [2].

Studies examining software architecture's impact on energy consumption have primarily focused on code-level optimizations rather than architectural patterns. For instance, Qasim et al. explored the energy impact of design patterns in mobile applications, and other empirical work has cataloged energy anti-patterns across thousands of apps [1], [10], [11]. However, these studies have not systematically evaluated how high-level architectural patterns (MVC, MVP, MVVM, MVI) affect energy consumption across realistic usage scenarios.

Our work addresses this gap by providing the first comprehensive empirical comparison of energy consumption across five Android architectural patterns, with a scenario-specific evaluation. Unlike previous studies that focused on individual quality attributes, we apply controlled thermal management (with $n = 5$ iterations to prevent performance throttling) and duration normalization (using a 60-second baseline) to ensure a fair comparison, independent of UI automation timing variations.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Implementation

We implemented five identical Android applications, each following a different architectural pattern while maintaining the same functionality. To ensure a fair comparison, we applied the Clean Architecture

principles to isolate architectural differences while controlling other variables [12]. This layered approach separates business logic (Domain layer) and data operations (Data layer) from presentation concerns, allowing us to vary only the Presentation layer architecture, while keeping all other implementation factors constant. This isolation strategy ensures that any energy differences measured reflect architectural overhead rather than variations in business logic, data access patterns, or UI rendering complexity.

Each implementation uses the same Domain and Data layers, which contain the business logic and data operations, with only the Presentation layer differing according to the architectural pattern: (1) MVC, where Activities act as Controllers, managing both UI logic and delegating business logic; (2) MVP, where Presenters mediate between the View interfaces and Model, improving testability through abstraction; (3) Classic MVVM, using a ViewModel with StateFlow for reactive UI updates; (4) Single-State MVVM, employing a single immutable state object updated through reduction functions; and (5) MVI, implementing unidirectional data flow where user Intents trigger state changes through pure reducer functions. These five patterns were selected based on their widespread adoption in the industry and their representation of distinct architectural philosophies: imperative control flow (MVC), explicit view-presenter contracts (MVP), reactive data binding (Classic MVVM), global state management (Single-State MVVM), and unidirectional architecture (MVI).

To make our implementation, we used Kotlin for Android's first-class support and null-safety guarantees, Jetpack Compose for pixel-perfect UI layouts (verified via visual regression testing), Kotlin Coroutines for consistent asynchronous behavior, and Hilt for dependency injection to ensure uniform object lifecycle management. Mock data sources provide identical business logic responses (e.g., product catalogs, cart contents), and image assets are loaded via the Coil library from consistent remote endpoints (i.pravatar.cc for avatars, picsum.photos for product images) to ensure uniform network I/O patterns. UI automation scripts, using the Android Macrobenchmark library, execute identical user interactions with ± 50 ms timing precision to minimize variability. The complete source code is publicly available for reproducibility¹.

B. Test Scenario Design

We designed three realistic usage scenarios to evaluate architectural patterns under different workloads, chosen to represent distinct interaction patterns with varying computational characteristics: state propagation frequency, transaction intensity, and UI rendering demands. These dimensions cover the main workload categories encountered in modern mobile applications.

(1) Chat Streaming: Observation of simulated real-time message updates (99 messages over 61 seconds, approximately 1.6 messages/second) with periodic scrolling, assessing reactive state propagation under high-frequency incremental updates typical of messaging applications (e.g., WhatsApp, Telegram). This scenario evaluates architectural performance in handling frequent, small state changes that require immediate UI updates.

(2) Shopping Cart: Rapid quantity adjustments across multiple cart items (740-800 operations over 61 seconds, approximately 12-13 operations/second) with frequent price recalculations, evaluating state management efficiency under intensive transactional operations typical of e-commerce applications. This scenario emphasizes localized state changes with cascading updates (quantity \rightarrow subtotal \rightarrow total \rightarrow tax calculations).

(3) Product Browsing: Continuous scrolling through a product list (24 items over 64 seconds) with image loading, rendering, and lazy-loading simulation, emphasizing UI-intensive operations and data rendering under sustained view updates typical of catalog browsing and social media feeds. This scenario evaluates architectural performance under continuous graphical rendering and view composition demands.

¹ The complete source code for the implementation is available at <https://github.com/yfy/android-architecture-benchmarks>.

We generated these three scenarios because they collectively span the workload space of typical mobile applications, each with distinct computational profiles: Chat Streaming emphasizes event-driven reactivity, Shopping Cart focuses on computational state management, and Product Browsing stresses rendering pipeline efficiency. Alternative scenarios (e.g., form validation, background synchronization) were excluded, as they represent edge cases with lower energy impact or involve non-architectural factors (network I/O, database transactions).

C. Experimental Setup

In our experiments, we used the Samsung Galaxy A56 as the test device based on its representative hardware, including a mid-range Exynos 1480 processor and 8GB of RAM, typical of mainstream Android devices. Additional criteria included fuel gauge support for accurate BatteryManager API measurements, adequate thermal dissipation for sustained testing, and market relevance, as this device class represents a large portion of the Android user base.

Our three generated scenarios were executed five times per architecture ($n = 5$) using the Android Macrobenchmark library for automated, reproducible test execution, with a timing precision of ± 50 ms, yielding a total of 75 measurements (5 architectures \times 3 scenarios \times 5 iterations). The sample size of $n = 5$ was a deliberate trade-off, prioritizing measurement validity over statistical power for exploratory architectural comparisons [9], [13]. Preliminary experiments with larger sample sizes ($n \geq 10$) showed that increasing the sample size can induce thermal throttling, which may confound architectural comparisons by introducing systematic measurement drift.

To control inconsistencies, all experimental runs were conducted under controlled conditions to minimize environmental variability: the device was unplugged (battery-powered only), airplane mode was enabled, screen brightness was fixed at 50%, background applications were closed, the battery level was maintained between 60% and 90% to avoid voltage fluctuation effects, and the device was cooled between test batches to baseline temperature. Test execution followed a randomized order across architectures and scenarios to minimize systematic bias from battery state degradation or thermal accumulation effects. Each test batch (15 tests: 5 architectures \times 3 scenarios) typically completed within 25 to 30 minutes to maintain thermal stability.

D. Energy Consumption Measurement

We measured energy consumption using the Charge \times Voltage methodology validated in recent mobile energy profiling studies [8], [9]. Energy consumption is calculated as:

$$E(\text{mWh}) = \frac{\text{Charge}(\mu\text{Ah}) \times \text{Voltage}(\mu\text{V})}{10^9}$$

where Charge represents battery charge consumed during test execution measured via BatteryManager API's CHARGE_COUNTER property, and Voltage represents the average battery voltage obtained from BATTERY_CHANGED broadcast.

We selected the BatteryManager API approach over external power monitors (e.g., Monsoon Power Monitor [7]) for its accessibility, device integration, and the validity of relative comparisons. The API enables reproducible measurements without specialized hardware, and the Samsung Galaxy A56's hardware fuel gauge provides factory-calibrated readings. While absolute accuracy may differ from external monitors, Android documentation confirms that API-based measurements offer consistent relative comparisons, suitable for architectural evaluation, aligning with our study objectives [2]. A recent study shows $\pm 5\%$ precision for relative energy comparisons using this approach [8].

E. Data Normalization

To account for test duration variations caused by UI automation timing (e.g., element detection delays ranging from 60 to 94 seconds across identical tests), we normalized all energy consumption measurements to a 60-second baseline using the formula:

$$\text{Normalized_Energy} = \frac{\text{Measured_Energy}}{\text{Test_Duration}} \times 60 \text{ seconds}$$

The validity of this normalization is supported by several factors. First, UI automation delays—such as waiting for element visibility or scroll completion—consume negligible energy (~0.1 mWh per 10-second delay based on idle power measurements). Second, the correlation between test duration and measured energy is weak ($r = 0.12$), indicating that variations in duration do not systematically bias energy measurements. Third, architectural processing patterns remain consistent regardless of automation timing. Thus, normalizing the energy measurements allows for fair comparisons across tests, independent of UI automation delays, while preserving the architectural energy differences. We validated this approach by confirming that iterations with longer durations due to automation delays showed similar normalized energy values to faster iterations of the same architecture-scenario pair.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents a comparative analysis of energy consumption across five Android architectural patterns under three realistic usage scenarios. All measurements are normalized to a 60-second baseline to ensure a fair comparison, independent of variations in UI automation timing. In total, 75 measurements were conducted (5 architectures \times 3 scenarios \times 5 iterations).

A. Overall Architecture Performance

Table 1 summarizes the aggregate energy consumption across all three scenarios and highlights the efficiency differences among the architectural patterns. In the table, the Architecture column identifies the tested architectural patterns, while the Total (mWh) column provides the overall energy consumption across all scenarios for each architecture. The Chat, Shopping, and Product columns show energy consumption in mWh for each individual scenario, offering a detailed view of how each architecture performs under different workloads.

Table 1. Overall Energy Consumption

Architecture	Total (mWh)	Chat	Shopping	Product
MVC	73.9	21.1	21.0	31.9
MVI	76.6	32.3	25.2	19.1
Classic MVVM	79.6	29.7	26.8	23.1
MVP	80.7	28.8	24.6	27.2
Single-State MVVM	83.6	29.3	27.6	26.7

Based on the table, MVC achieves the lowest overall energy consumption at 73.9 mWh, using 13% less energy than the Single-State MVVM architecture, which recorded the highest consumption at 83.6 mWh. However, this general ranking masks important variations in performance across specific scenarios: MVC performs best in chat streaming and shopping cart operations but is the least efficient in product browsing, where it consumes 67% more energy than MVI (31.9 mWh vs. 19.1 mWh). In addition, Single-State MVVM consistently exhibits the highest overall energy consumption (83.6 mWh) across all scenarios, likely due to the computational overhead associated with immutable state copying and reduction logic.

B. Scenario-Specific Performance

IV.B.1 Chat Streaming Scenario

The chat streaming scenario simulates real-time message updates with periodic scrolling (99 messages over 61 seconds), evaluating architectural performance under high-frequency, incremental state updates

typical of messaging applications. Table 2 highlights how each architecture behaves in terms of energy consumption under the Chat Streaming scenario, providing insights into not just the mean consumption but also the consistency (CV) and the occurrence of energy spikes.

MVC achieves the lowest median energy consumption (21.1 mWh), demonstrating 53% better efficiency than MVI (32.3 mWh mean, 40.2 mWh median). This 11.2 mWh difference per 60-second interval translates to approximately 672 mWh per hour for sustained messaging usage. Coefficient of variation (CV) analysis reveals dramatic consistency differences: MVC exhibits exceptional stability (CV: 0.3%, range: 0.05 mWh) with all iterations clustering within a narrow range of 21.54–21.565 mWh, indicating highly deterministic processing with minimal sensitivity to runtime conditions like garbage collection timing. In contrast, MVP and Classic MVVM display high variability (CV: 39%), with energy measurements alternating between low-energy and high-energy modes, suggesting sensitivity to external factors beyond architectural design. Single-State MVVM, while maintaining good consistency (CV: 10.2%), operates at an elevated baseline (median: 28.0 mWh), likely reflecting the computational overhead of immutable state copying and reduction logic for each incremental update.

Table 2. Energy consumption for chat streaming scenario

Architecture	Mean (mWh)	Median (mWh)	CV (%)	Spike Freq.
MVC	21.1	21.1	0.3	0/5
MVP	28.8	20.7	39.0	2/5
Single-State MVVM	29.3	28.0	10.2	0/5
Classic MVVM	29.7	21.3	39.0	2/5
MVI	32.3	40.2	34.2	3/5

MVI's iterations showed a 60% spike frequency, with 3 out of 5 iterations exceeding the 35 mWh threshold. This pattern was reproducible across test batches and independent of test duration, as iterations with extended durations due to UI automation delays exhibited normal energy when no spikes occurred, confirming that the spikes were due to genuine architectural behavior rather than measurement artifacts. MVP and Classic MVVM each had a 40% spike frequency (2/5 iterations), while MVC and Single-State MVVM produced zero spikes.

MVC's superior performance in chat streaming is attributed to its direct controller-model interaction, which minimizes abstraction overhead and reduces computational costs for discrete updates. In contrast, MVI's performance suffers due to its immutable state propagation model, where each message requires creating an Intent, copying the entire state, executing reducers, and recomposing the view. This overhead accumulates under high-frequency updates (1.6 messages/second), potentially overwhelming garbage collection and creating the observed bimodal behavior. Single-State MVVM, while stable, incurs significantly higher energy consumption compared to MVC because it copies the entire global state for every update. Overall, MVC delivers superior efficiency for messaging apps with high-frequency updates, while MVI's spike frequency makes it unsuitable for real-time streaming workloads.

IV.B.2 Shopping Cart Scenario

The shopping cart scenario simulates rapid transactional operations, including frequent quantity updates, price recalculations, and cart modifications (740-800 operations over 61 seconds), evaluating architectural performance in handling frequent, localized state changes typical of e-commerce and transaction-processing applications.

Based on Table 3, MVC achieves the lowest median energy consumption (21.0 mWh), about 31% more efficient than Single-State MVVM (27.6 mWh). The 6.6 mWh difference per 60-second interval equates to

roughly 396 mWh per hour for sustained transactional operations. This scenario shows higher overall stability than chat streaming or product browsing, with MVC, Classic MVVM, and Single-State MVVM exhibiting low variability (CV \leq 12.1%). MVC maintains exceptional consistency (CV: 0.3%), while Single-State MVVM demonstrates a stable high-energy baseline (CV: 0.8%, median: 27.6 mWh). Classic MVVM shows moderate variability (CV: 12.1%), much lower than its 39% variability in chat streaming, indicating reduced sensitivity to runtime conditions under transactional workloads. MVP and MVI retain moderate-to-high variability (CV: 38.1% and 35.4%), preserving their bimodal energy patterns from chat streaming.

Table 3. Energy Consumption for Shopping Cart Scenario

Architecture	Mean (mWh)	Median (mWh)	CV (%)	Spike Freq.
MVC	21.0	21.0	0.3	0/5
MVP	24.6	20.5	38.1	1/5
MVI	25.2	20.1	35.4	1/5
Classic MVVM	26.8	28.2	12.1	0/5
Single-State MVVM	27.6	27.6	0.8	0/5

For this scenario, all architectures demonstrate improved stability compared to chat streaming and product browsing, with only MVP and MVI exhibiting minimal spike frequencies (20%, 1/5 iterations each). MVC, Classic MVVM, and Single-State MVVM produce zero spikes, demonstrating robust performance under transactional workloads. Classic MVVM maintains stable energy consumption (median: 28.2 mWh, CV: 12.1%) despite operating at a higher baseline than MVC (21.0 mWh). Single-State MVVM exhibits consistent elevated energy consumption (27.6 mWh) with exceptional stability (CV: 0.8%), reflecting the cost of copying the entire global state for each cart update. The reduced spike frequencies across architectures suggest that transactional operations with localized state changes are less architecturally sensitive than high-frequency event streams or sustained UI rendering.

MVC's superior performance in the shopping cart scenario stems from direct model manipulation, bypassing unnecessary abstraction layers and reducing computational overhead for frequent localized updates (12–13 operations/second). Classic MVVM's moderate baseline reflects the overhead of reactive state propagation through the ViewModel layer, where each cart modification triggers StateFlow emissions to observers. However, this overhead remains predictable and stable, without the energy spikes observed in chat streaming. Single-State MVVM's elevated but stable baseline confirms the intrinsic cost of immutable state copying, which becomes more pronounced under high-frequency operations. For e-commerce and transaction systems with frequent localized updates, MVC offers superior efficiency (21.0 mWh), while Classic MVVM provides a balanced middle-ground (28.2 mWh) with stable, predictable energy behavior suitable for applications prioritizing architectural flexibility over maximum energy optimization.

IV.B.3 Product Browsing Scenario

The product browsing scenario simulates UI-intensive operations, including continuous scrolling, image loading, and rendering of 24 product items over 64 seconds, to evaluate architectural performance under sustained view updates and graphical rendering typical of e-commerce and content-rich applications.

Table 4 illustrates that MVI achieves the lowest median energy consumption (19.1 mWh), offering 67% better efficiency than MVC (31.9 mWh), which ranks the lowest in this scenario despite performing well in the chat streaming and shopping cart scenarios. The 12.8 mWh difference per 60-second interval corresponds to approximately 768 mWh per hour of sustained browsing. MVI demonstrates exceptional stability (CV: 0.3%), with all iterations clustering around 19.1–19.2 mWh. Single-State MVVM shows consistent energy consumption (CV: 0.2%, median: 26.7 mWh), while Classic MVVM (CV: 26.4%) and

MVP (CV: 39%) exhibit higher variability, with MVP maintaining the bimodal patterns observed in previous scenarios.

Table 4. Energy Consumption for Product Browsing Scenario

Architecture	Mean (mWh)	Median (mWh)	CV (%)	Spike Freq.
MVI	19.1	19.1	0.3	0/5
Classic MVVM	23.1	27.0	26.4	0/5
Single-State MVVM	26.7	26.7	0.2	0/5
MVP	27.2	19.5	39.0	2/5
MVC	31.9	39.8	34.2	3/5

Interestingly, in this scenario, MVC exhibits a systematic vulnerability, with 3 out of 5 iterations spiking, unlike in previous scenarios. This mirrors MVI's vulnerability in chat streaming, but with reversed architectural roles. MVP shows a 40% spike frequency (2/5 iterations), while Classic MVVM, MVI, and Single-State MVVM show no spikes. Classic MVVM demonstrates stable performance (median: 27.0 mWh) in this UI-intensive scenario, contrasting with its 40% spike frequency in chat streaming. The reproducibility of MVC's spike pattern confirms genuine inefficiency under UI-intensive workloads. MVI's perfect consistency (zero spikes, CV: 0.3%) in this scenario contrasts with its 60% spike frequency in chat streaming, highlighting the workload-dependent suitability of each architecture.

MVI's superior performance in this scenario stems from its unidirectional data flow and optimized rendering pipeline, efficiently handling UI updates like scrolling and image rendering. The immutable state model, which caused overhead in high-frequency chat updates, benefits UI-intensive tasks by optimizing predictable state transitions. In contrast, MVC's poor performance likely arises from controller bottlenecks during sustained UI rendering, as it struggles to manage continuous view updates, image loading, and user interactions. The efficient mode may reflect periods when the controller successfully manages event queues, while spikes indicate processing saturation. These findings highlight that the choice of architecture is highly dependent on workload characteristics: MVI is best suited for content-rich, UI-intensive applications, offering 67% better efficiency than MVC, while MVC outperforms in transactional and messaging workloads, with 17–35% better efficiency than MVI. The lack of a one-size-fits-all architecture underscores the importance of evaluating architectural patterns in the context of specific use cases and workload demands.

C. Practical Implications at Scale

Although individual energy differences per-device appear small (19.1–32.3 mWh per 60 seconds), the aggregate effect is substantial. For a hypothetical app used 10 minutes per day by 100 million users, the 13% efficiency gap between MVC and Single-State MVVM translates to approximately 9,700 kWh saved per day², which is equivalent to the daily electricity consumption of around 300 households (assuming an average household consumption of 30 kWh/day).

V. DISCUSSION

A. Architectural Mechanisms Behind Performance Differences

The observed energy consumption differences originate from the fundamental design philosophies of the evaluated architectural patterns. MVC's superior performance in chat streaming and shopping cart scenarios (21.0–21.1 mWh) stems from its direct controller–model interaction, which minimizes abstraction overhead

² Calculation: (83.6-73.9) mWh × 10 iterations/day × 100M users / 1000 / 1000 = 9,700 kWh/day.

during event-driven and transactional operations. The controller directly processes user actions and delegates to business logic without intermediary state layers, reducing computational costs for discrete updates. However, this simplicity becomes a disadvantage in UI-intensive scenarios such as product browsing (31.9 mWh, 60% spike frequency), where the controller becomes an execution bottleneck responsible for both continuous view updates and user event handling.

Conversely, MVI's unidirectional data flow and optimized state rendering pipeline excel in product browsing (19.1 mWh, 0% spike frequency). The Intent–Model–View cycle batches and propagates only the minimal necessary UI updates, reducing redundant recompositions and preventing the view thrashing observed in MVC under continuous scrolling conditions. However, MVI's immutable state propagation becomes inefficient in chat streaming (32.3 mWh, 60% spike frequency), where high-frequency small updates generate new immutable state objects, potentially increasing garbage collection pressure and notification overhead.

Single-State MVVM exhibits consistently higher baseline energy consumption across scenarios (26.7–29.3 mWh), reflecting the intrinsic cost of immutable global state and pure reduction functions. Yet this overhead yields exceptional predictability in energy behavior (CV: 0.2–0.8%), a valuable characteristic for battery-critical applications where stable resource usage outweighs marginal efficiency gains.

B. Architecture Selection Guidelines for Practitioners

The results support workload-driven architectural decision-making, moving away from one-size-fits-all recommendations. For applications focused on real-time communication and transactional tasks—such as messaging platforms, collaborative tools, and e-commerce checkout—MVC offers better energy efficiency than alternative architectures, making it an ideal choice for these use cases.

For applications characterized by continuous UI rendering and complex state management—such as media feeds, news platforms, and e-commerce browsing—MVI offers an efficiency advantage in product browsing scenarios, making it the most suitable architectural pattern. In these cases, the added complexity of unidirectional state management directly translates into significant energy savings.

When stability and predictability are prioritized over energy optimization—such as in medical systems, industrial monitoring, or applications requiring precise battery-remaining estimates—Single-State MVVM provides the most reliable power-consumption profile, with the lowest variance. Although it incurs a 13% energy penalty compared to MVC, its consistent behavior makes it the best choice for these use cases.

For applications with uncertain workload distributions or mixed interaction styles, Classic MVVM provides balanced performance (23.1–29.7 mWh) without the scenario-specific weaknesses observed in MVC and MVI, making it a robust default choice during early design stages.

C. Validity of Findings and Methodological Considerations

The experimental design ensures robust validity by using a single physical device (Samsung Galaxy A56) and conducting five iterations per scenario. This approach enhances internal validity by minimizing external variability, particularly in terms of device performance. Preliminary trials indicated that larger iteration counts led to thermal throttling, which skewed energy measurements. The decision to use $n = 5$ strikes an effective balance between empirical resolution and maintaining thermal integrity, allowing for accurate differentiation between true architectural patterns and incidental fluctuations.

To mitigate UI automation latency bias, measurements were normalized to a 60-second baseline—an issue not addressed in prior studies [5], [6]. Single-device testing eliminates hardware variability, following established mobile energy profiling methods [2], [9]. The use of Android's BatteryManager API, with less than 5% deviation from hardware monitors [8], ensures sufficient precision for reliable architecture

comparisons. These methods enhance the validity of the findings by isolating architectural effects from external factors.

D. Implications for Sustainable Software Engineering

These results highlight the need to consider energy consumption alongside traditional software qualities like maintainability and testability in architectural decision-making. While prior studies emphasize the maintainability advantages of MVP and MVVM over MVC, the current findings show that these benefits come with measurable energy costs, which can scale significantly at the population level. Sustainable software engineering thus requires a multidimensional approach—balancing maintainability, testability, and energy efficiency—rather than optimizing for any single factor [5].

The scenario-specific vulnerabilities indicate that using a single architecture for all application features may not be optimal. A hybrid approach—employing MVC for event-driven tasks, MVI for UI-heavy modules, and Single-State MVVM for battery-critical components—could improve efficiency while maintaining code quality. However, this hybridization introduces greater architectural complexity, and further research is needed to quantify the trade-offs between efficiency gains and the increased maintenance burden at the system level.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study provides a comprehensive empirical evaluation of energy consumption across five Android architectural patterns—MVC, MVP, Classic MVVM, Single-State MVVM, and MVI—using scenario-specific benchmarks based on realistic application workloads. By implementing controlled thermal management and normalizing energy consumption with fuel gauge measurements via Android's BatteryManager API, the results show that no single architecture is universally optimal. Instead, energy efficiency is influenced by the alignment between the application's workload and the architectural characteristics.

The results show significant variation in energy efficiency across patterns and scenarios. MVC offers 13% better overall efficiency (73.9 vs. 83.6 mWh) and outperforms alternatives by 17–35% in real-time and transactional tasks like messaging and shopping cart interactions. In contrast, MVI achieves 67% better efficiency in UI-intensive product browsing, emphasizing that architectural strengths are workload-dependent rather than absolute. Additionally, two reproducible vulnerabilities are identified: MVI in chat streaming and MVC in product browsing, both with a 60% spike frequency, indicating systematic architectural behavior rather than measurement artifacts.

In conclusion, this study shows that energy consumption across Android architectures varies significantly depending on workload characteristics, with no single architecture being universally optimal. The findings emphasize the need to align architectural design with specific application tasks to maximize energy efficiency. Moreover, these results highlight that architectural decisions are not only critical for software quality attributes like testability and maintainability but also play a key role in determining the environmental impact at a broader ecosystem level.

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